

SCHOOLTEACHERS PERCEPTIONS OF EDUCATION DISCIPLINE POLICY ON LEARNERS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SELECTED SOUTH AFRICAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

This paper summarizes the schoolteachers' perceptions of education discipline policy on learners' academic performance in selected South African Secondary Schools. The objective of the study was to explore and describe the schoolteachers' perceptions of education discipline policy on learners' academic performance in selected South African Secondary Schools. A qualitative research method was chosen and assisted with an understanding of the participants' perceptions of education discipline policy on learners' academic performance. Purposeful sampling was used to identify the five public Secondary Schools that performed poorly. The participants comprised of 15 schoolteachers. Three schoolteachers were selected from the five secondary schools. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and constant comparative analysis performed during analysis. Discipline was perceived to be a challenge, and academic performance was found to be low. The implementation of learner discipline policy required monitoring and reviewing academic performance to avoid disparity between policy and practice.

Keywords: Academic performance, education discipline policy, learners, perceptions, schoolteachers, secondary schools

1. Introduction

A lack of learner discipline may destroy the future of learners and leads to unsuccessful education. Discipline is significant for effective and efficient teaching and learning. Poor academic performance in public Secondary Schools in the study area was a concern. Since the abolition of corporal punishment and the proclamation of the new disciplinary system, public schools seem to be in shambles (Republic South African Act 33 of 1997). The researchers focused on the perceptions of schoolteachers regarding education policy on learner discipline in public Secondary Schools.

Nash, Schlosser and Scarr (2016) conducted a study on teachers' perceptions of disruptive behavior in schools: a psychological perspective. The study revealed that for the most troubled pupils, effective behavior management at schools necessitates a more nurturing and collaborative approach alongside current disciplinary policy.

According to the study conducted by Lumato and Mwila (2022) at Tanzania on stakeholders' perceptions about the use of alternative punishment in maintaining school discipline, good school discipline was found to be a result of rules and moral instructions that form behavioural strategies appropriate to the regulation of children and the maintenance of order in schools. Discipline is a multidimensional phenomenon that maybe defined from various perspectives (Edinyang, 2017). However, in this article, it is viewed from one perspective being learner discipline.

Learner discipline is a difficult concept to define as it is multifaceted and maybe viewed from different perspectives (Jinot, 2017). Traditionally, it is defined as the degree of order and structure that is required to maintain socially acceptable behavior among students (Ugboko & Adediwura, 2012). So, discipline means the absence of misbehavior and the student's responsibility to make the difference between right and wrong, and between acceptable and unacceptable behavior at school and in the society.

Discipline is necessity for successful teaching and learning in schools and a subject of concern to teachers, parents, and schools. Wherever discipline is adjudged to be good, there will be improved academic performance. Therefore, discipline is vital for effective school management and the accomplishment of the goal of school (Ama, Moorad & Mukhopadyay, 2020). However, there are a lot of unanswered questions regarding the reasons learners misbehave in schools leading to them being suspended or expelled and these affect the quality and equity in Basic Education, particularly in public Secondary Schools. The perceptions of schoolteachers regarding education policy on learner discipline can be of tremendous use in providing answers to questions on poor academic performance in Basic Education.

The education system plays a fundamental role in ensuring that there is learner discipline in schools. However, internal factors of the public Secondary Schools and the way the education system is structured have significant impact on learner behavior (Jinot, 2017). It should be noted that this article limits itself to education policy on learner discipline. The findings of the study conducted in Mauritius revealed lack of discipline as the actual number one school problem in both Secondary Schools and Primary Schools. It is one of the main factors that hamper the effective running of schools. The degradation is the result of the fact that since the Education Regulations (1957), all the education reforms or plans rarely mention discipline as a school problem (Jinot, 2017).

The role of schoolteachers in ensuring that learners imbibe discipline from home and in schools cannot be overemphasized. Good performance of schools and learners is very much linked to participation of all stakeholders (parents, teachers, learners, Parent Teachers Associations, Student Governing Bodies (SGBs), government departments, community, learners, and private sector) in education (Ama et al., 2020).

Otu, Obun and Joseph (2019) in their study on students' perception towards management of discipline and their academic performance in Cross River State found that students with negative perception towards the management of suspension and expulsion, did not perform well academically. Those who had a positive perception of the management of suspension and expulsion did better academically.

There are several factors or problems that hinder learners from receiving a good standard of education such as the lack of parental participation in the education of their children and the functioning of SGBs which can be described as weak. Parents do not have access to familiarize themselves with the school curriculum or be involved in the activities of the schools. The teachers are not aware of how to effectively involve parents in the academic performance of the learners (Stelmack, n.d).

According to Ama et al. (2020), there is always a tendency for affluent parents to be involved in school more often and in positive ways, whereas economically distressed parents have limited contact with schools, and usually in situations dealing with students' achievement or behavior. Parents who are less educated and have low-income often adopt some survival strategies. They either focus on their family or sometimes may not have enough time to engage in home-school work that could be helpful in improving the child's schooling.

2. Methodology

According (Sreekumar, 2023) research methodology is a process by which researchers design their study so that they can achieve their objectives using selected research instruments. The researchers used schoolteachers because of their knowledge and awareness of the current situation of implementing the national education policies in their respective schools. A qualitative method was chosen as it assisted the researchers to understand the experiences of research participants and their social cultural context.

2.1 Design

Sepasgozar et al. (2018) declare that a research design is a universal strategy for solving a research problem and it provides an overall structure for the procedures' researchers follow, the data the researchers collect and the analysis the researchers conduct. Korstjens (2018) indicates that research design shows how the objectives will be attained and how they will assist in reaching a conclusion or solution to the research problem. Sileyew (2019) asserts that research design intends to provide an appropriate framework for a study.

A qualitative research design assisted in obtaining reliable information directly from the primary sources. The researchers chose this method because of its comprehensiveness that facilitated gathering as much data as possible and analyzing it for the justification and conviction of the problem under investigation.

2.2 Setting

Majid (2018) defines the study setting as a location where the study is conducted. The authors assert that it is important to understand the nature, environment, and logistics of the study as these aspects may influence how the research is carried out. The study was conducted in Secondary Schools that were still existing with ill-discipline and poor learners' academic performance.

2.3 Sampling

Sampling is the process by which a researcher carefully selects through probabilistic and non-probabilistic methods several individual items from a larger population of interest for a closer study (Mweshi & Sakyi, 2020). Purposive sampling was chosen for the study and consisted of the poorly performing five public Secondary Schools regarding academic performance (Department of Basic Education, 2012). The participants included a sample of three stakeholders per school. The principals were requested to suggest individuals, in the categories of teachers who possessed the necessary attributes regarding the topic about school policies.

2.4 Data collection

Data collection is the process of gathering and measuring information on variables of interest, in an established systematic fashion that enables one to answer stated questions, test hypotheses, and evaluate outcome (Kabir, 2016). Semi-structured interviews were used to convert data into the information directly provided by the participants. Providing access to what is inside a person's mind makes it possible to measure what a person knows (Mukwambo, 2016).

The interviews were conducted to ensure that the participants were free to express their perceptions and opinions about the effects of education discipline policy on academic performance of schools, with a focus on the policy of learner discipline. The schoolteachers were interviewed in their staffrooms. The interviews lasted for approximately 45 minutes per interviewee.

2.5 Data analysis

Sharma (2018) defines data analysis as the process of developing answers to questions through the examination and interpretation of data. Constant Comparative Analysis was used to analyse data. It is a data analysis process whereby each interpretation and finding are compared to existing findings as it emerges from the data analysed (Benton, 2017). Inductive data coding process was used for categorizing and comparing qualitative data for analysis purposes.

Codes were assigned to the selected chosen schools first and then raw descriptive responses from the participants checked and sorted to identify similar phrases. Similar responses by participants in the five public Secondary Schools were identified, grouped, and summarized, to produce the transcripts. Contrasting data were also included. Pseudo names V, W, X, Y and Z were allocated to the Secondary Schools to discuss their characteristics. The participants' biographies were tabulated using Schoolteacher a to Schoolteacher o (Sta -Sto), for teachers respectively.

2.6 Trustworthiness

The study followed Guba and Lincoln's (1985) criteria for ensuring trustworthiness as cited by Polit and Beck (2022). These criteria are credibility, transferability, dependability, confirmability, and authenticity.

Credibility is defined by Leedy (2019) as the confidence that can be placed in the truth of the research findings. The participants were selected purposively to produce accurate findings because valid findings are credible. Member checks were also carried out to eliminate bias when analysing and interpreting the results. The analysed data were then sent back to the participants for them to evaluate the interpretation of the findings and to comment on the interpretation of their views on the research questions.

Korstjens and Moser (2017) assert that transferability refers to the degree to which the findings of qualitative research can be transferred to other contexts or settings with other respondents. The biographical details of the participants, the research setting, data collection method and data analysis were fully described to ensure transferability.

Dependability refers to the stability of data over time. It involves participants' evaluation of the findings, interpretation, and recommendations of the study such that all are supported by the data as received from participants of the study (Korstjens & Moser, 2017). The field notes were used during the interviews to document aspects that could not be audio-recorded. All the audio-recorded interviews were independently transcribed and analysed by an independent coder.

Confirmability is the extent to which the findings and conclusions of the study are supported by the data generated for the purpose of the study (Hammond & Wellington, 2021). The recorded information represented the voice of the participants, not the researchers.

Authenticity refers to the extent to which researchers fairly and faithfully show a range of different realities (Guba & Lincoln, 1994). Besides a description of the participants, authenticity was ensured by using participants' direct quotations verbatim and an audit trail.

2.7 Ethical consideration

Research ethics refers to the application of a moral Code of Conduct, where participants are the focus of empirical research (Biggam, 2018). In ethical consideration involving humans the researchers should care for the rights of human population, safeguard the well-being of research respondents, understand areas of investigation including evaluating the research quality (India Centre for Media Studies-Institutional Review Board (CMS-IRB), 2022).

Letters for requesting permission to conduct the study were compiled and emailed to the Department of Education (DoE). Request letters were sent to the principals of the selected public Secondary Schools for asking permission to conduct the research in the schools.

The informed consent letters were issued and explained to the participants in the meetings at the schools. Explanation of what was expected from the participants in terms of participation was done and the objective of the research was also mentioned.

Regarding personal harm to participants, researchers informed the participants beforehand about the potential impact of the investigation to allow them to withdraw from the inquiry if they so wish.

3. Findings

To ensure that the principal findings analysed in the study were in line with the research title and objective, a literature preview on the effect of national education policies on learner discipline and academic performance was conducted. The perceptions of schoolteachers on national education policies such as learner discipline policy on learner discipline and academic performance was carried out.

The researchers presented the participants' views without adding any information that was not part of the participants' responses as it would no longer be the original data. However, the data presented were manipulated through coding, meaning they were sorted, grouped, linked, summarized, and interpreted. The original words of the participants are italicized and presented in verbatim form. This is supported by Ranuka and Jonathan (2015) by specifying that interview transcripts must not be rephrased to be grammatically correct, and the raw data must not be summarized.

Table 1: Schoolteachers a to Schoolteacher o (Codes Sta-Sto)

School	Schoolteacher	Gender	Age group	Highest qualification	Training on new discipline policy
V	Sta	M	35-50	STD	No
	Stb	F	35-50	STD	No
	Stc	M	35-50	BA-ED	No
W	Std	M	35-50	BA; PTC	No
	Ste	M	51-60	BA; STD	No
	Stf	F	35-50	BA; HED	No
X	Stg	F	35-50	BTECH	No
	Sth	F	20-34	BA-HONS; BA-ED	No
	Sti	F	35-50	BA; STD	No
Y	Stj	M	35-50	STD	No
	Stk	F	35-50	BA-ED	No
	Stl	M	51-65	BA; STD	No
Z	Stm	F	35-50	BA; HED	No
	Stn	F	20-34	BA-ED	No
	Sto	F	35-50	STD	No

Central Question:

What is your perception of education discipline policy on learner academic performance in your Secondary School?

W(Stf) said:

The classrooms are packed to capacity, and I cannot move between the desks easily. Individual attendance of learners is not possible; school attendance is irregular. The shortage of textbooks is another challenge. I make

them share the textbooks, but before sharing, they make noise first. I make those who make noise to face the wall up until the end of the period or write down their names and give them punishment such as cleaning classrooms. The learners who disturb the lesson, who do not do schoolwork, I make them sit on the floor or stand in front and face the chalkboard or scrub the floor. Sometimes I invite their parents to school to tell them about what their children do at school. I make sure I am thoroughly prepared when I go to class to arouse their interest and eliminate class disruption. I engage and involve all learners in the lesson by asking questions, giving them pictures to interpret and assignments to complete in class. I become exhausted at the end of each school day. All these strategies become a futile exercise because eventually, they fail to dismantle. Only 6% of learners in Grade 8 passed last year, the rest were progressed. (F, 35-50 years)

Grade teacher in school **W** mentioned that their school has learner overcrowding in the classrooms, which results in the shortage of teaching learning material such as textbooks. This then triggers disciplinary problems when sharing the resources. Learners do not pass, but they are progressed in terms of the national education acceleration or progression policy.

This is what participant **Y(Stj)** had to say:

We teach too many classes, and it becomes difficult to know the learners by their names to call them by to discourage the misbehavior. One may imagine a teacher teaching eight classes of 50 learners each. About 300 learners, it is quite a significant number to be able to manage such learners effectively, without disciplinary problems which disrupt classes and result in poor academic performance. Correct teacher-learner ratios coupled with the Code of Conduct would be the only answers to proper behavior. But it needs to be correctly developed and implemented with systems in place, to be effective. It works for the former model C schools to produce excellent results, always 100% pass rate. It could work for us. (M, 35-50 years)

Y(Stj) echoed **W(Stf)** by stating that the teacher-learner ratio at their school was also higher than the policy requirement. According to **Y(Stj)**, their school did not have a Code of Conduct. Teacher **Y(Stj)** recommends that their school should have disciplinary systems in place. A low student-teacher ratio can allow the child to receive more individualized attention from the teacher, because they have fewer learners to monitor, and the teachers tend to spend less time on classroom management issues, such as ill-discipline. This would enhance the child's test scores and provide lasting academic benefits (Brozak, 2017). The (Public Education Center (PEC), 2018) confirms Brozak's assertion by adding that classes of not more than 15 to 18 learners seem to provide learners with the best benefits regarding achievement.

Z(Stn) pointed out that:

No Code of Conduct, no good discipline, and no good results. Appropriate action needs to be taken against learners who misbehave. Because the behavioral problem might recur if not dealt with accordingly. A comprehensive Code of Conduct must be developed to deal with all sorts of misconduct. All parties need to have understood on where they stand regarding disciplinary problems. The strategies which I am using to discipline the learners are not effective because I never saw a Code of Conduct at our school. (F, 20-34 years)

School **Z** did not have a Code of Conduct. **Stn's** class rules were not cascaded from the Code of Conduct which means in this school, rules differ from teacher to teacher, and there is a possibility that other teachers might not have any. Their school needed to have a Code of Conduct. The Code of Conduct had to be clarified to all parties to be on the same page or to have a common understanding when implementing it.

X(Sti) said:

We used to sing and pray for the children before we conduct our morning briefings and we used to teach them good morals at the assembly gathering, they behaved in an acceptable manner and showed respect. Our principal announced to us in the meeting that we must sing the national anthem in meetings and at learner assemblies. Ever since then the learner no longer discriminates between right and wrong. They don't greet anyone, and they are no longer scared of us. When I make them aware that what they are doing is wrong, they wonder, they say why madam? They don't see any wrong and those who are worse (COSAS), tell us that they are not afraid of us because the school is theirs. These children have so much confidence to undermine authority. When we report them to the district office, we are told to bring them closer to us. They don't explain how we can bring them closer. We fear these kids. (F, 35-50 years)

X(Sti) pointed to the replacement of the Christian doctrine by the national anthem as a source of all the misconduct that is happening in their school. Learners are ignorant of good morals. This increased the high failure rate, which led to progression.

X(Sth) indicated that:

I am not sure because I don't read policies. I want to be honest. What is the use, laws are written in English first language? I struggle to understand English second language which I did at school. The language in which the policies are written needs to be explained to me by specialists. It is challenging. What I heard from the principal is that

policy says we can no longer beat up learners. What do we do with naughty learners then? When we report them to the principal, he shifts the problem to HODs and say we must follow protocol. We are frustrated. Learners bunk classes, they sit in the toilets, gamble, and do drugs there. We see them on footage. (F, 20-34 years)

X(StH) gave a hesitant answer to the question due to the uncertainty based on their ignorance on school policies, because they do not understand Law jargon. They could no longer beat up children. Policies need to be taught for better understanding.

X(Sti) expressed:

The new discipline policy has a negative impact towards learner discipline because the kids are out of control. Late coming is rife. School starts at 8H45 but you will find learners dragging their feet to school up until 09H30, that is during period 3. When we close the gate during ground duty, they push us and the gate wide open and then proceed to class. They also pushed the SGB chairperson one day, and he could not take any further step against them. Most of the learners do not their schoolwork; they do not respect their teachers; they do not bring their textbooks to school while others are very bully. We hear from COSAS whether the school will function normally for the day or not. (F, 35-50 years)

The teacher thought it is the use of the Code of Conduct that sparks ill-discipline. Due to the misunderstanding of how the discipline policy works. Teacher X(Sti) also believes the new education policies ripped them off the means to punish the learners because it provides a positive way of maintaining discipline in schools.

V(Stc) said:

My perception is that they do have an impact because some of the learners do not listen ever since these new education policies were introduced. I report them to the principal or call their parents. Some learners refuse to take punishment, and it becomes difficult to discipline them thoroughly, they are also humiliating us. Others enjoy punishment which makes all the effort not effective. Some parents are not interested in their children's work. They are not involved in the education of their children. When we invite them to school through letters, they do not turn up. (M, 35-50 years)

The blame for learners who no longer obey teachers is put on the emergence of the new education policies after corporal punishment as repealed. Learners who belong to the student organisations such as COSAS are more informed about education policies that affect them. If they notice something that is unprocedural, they defy the teacher by refusing to take punishment, knowing very well that the HOD will dismiss the case. The no-fee policy also contributes to parents adopting a 'do not care' attitude and not giving support to teachers.

Y(Stk) presented:

I think the discipline policy is only focusing on the teacher than on the learner. The policy will end up punishing the teachers than disciplining the learners. It instils fear to us, and we will, therefore leave the learners to do as they please and end up failing. It gives the learners all the rights to disrespect us and put us mostly at a disadvantage. I feel that learners are overprotected by education law. As a result, they misbehave. (F, 35-50 years)

The teacher seemed to confuse corporal punishment with the Code of Conduct by stating that 'you might get charged for disciplining the learner'. You get charged when you beat the learner, but your case gets dismissed if one did not allow the correct procedure to discipline a learner'. It is ignorance of how the policy works that created fear to implement it because the participant said it protects the child and punishes the teacher.

Z(Sto) said:

It is time-consuming to discipline these learners, which impacts negatively on the time allocated to teach them what they are here for. Mostly, the learners are aware of their right and do not know their responsibilities or just ignore them. They are aware that they are overprotected by the law and there is not much I can do about it. I referred a learner to the class rules after breaking the rules and he said to me which rules are you talking about? I do not know anything about the rules. The learners who are stubborn, do not want to listen, they tell me about COSAS that they report me to it. They refuse to cooperate, and there is little that you can do. (F, Age 35-50)

The disciplinary process impacted negatively on contact time. Most of the time is consumed by learner discipline only as compared to other classroom activities including teaching, which is about 50% of contact time (Higton, 2017). The teacher showed a misunderstanding of the Code of Conduct.

4. Discussion

The study found that discipline was perceived to be a challenge, and academic performance was found to be low. The implementation of learner discipline policy required monitoring and reviewing academic performance to avoid disparity between policy and practice.

Overcrowding is the source of all the disciplinary problems and poor performance in schools because the teacher loses control over all learners. Some disrupt the class while hiding behind the others. As a result of overcrowding, there will be a shortage of resources such as textbooks and furniture, followed by fights over seats

because they cannot be shared. The teacher-learner ratio of 1:35 for public schools (Meier, 2017), is a quiet significant number when compared to the American and British ratios of 1:20 including the private schools around, where the very same public-school teachers take their children to classroom.

The consequences of teacher-learner ratios exceeding the quota implies that the number of learners in class exceeds the education policy limit. Discipline ought to be maintained in schools to ensure that the education of learners proceeds without disruptive behavior and offences. Its goal is to teach and lead the learners to self-discipline. Thus, in managing the school environment, a system of disciplining proactively and constructively should be implemented rather than punishment (Ebrahim, 2018).

Teacher **Z(Stn)** did not know the Code of Conduct of their school. She provided a routine self-developed strategy with an attempt to improve discipline in class, which might be a tedious and time-consuming exercise. However, Shaloway (2015) and Subbiah (2015) support these strategies because they can reduce disciplinary problems in the classroom.

The religious policy in education is outside the scope of this article and still needs further research. The researchers thought a moral ground is needed to teach good morals to learners (Rens, 2016). Singing the national anthem will not assist in any way to improve learner behavior. Schools could rather develop school songs in which good morals are enshrined, or let learners recite the Code of Conduct during detention sessions as in the case of the American lawyer, Thurgood Marshall.

According to responses of **X(Sth)**, the blame was put on teachers' ignorance of not reading school policies because of jargon. In this case, it is the law language that also makes it difficult to understand the Education law course. Consequently, teachers become reluctant to read these new policies. This condition makes education policies inaccessible to many readers. All the stakeholders, not teachers only, need to be trained to have a better understanding of the education policies.

X(Sti) expressed their views about the impact of the discipline on maintaining order in their school. They could not perceive that the cause of ill-discipline could be the inability to develop and implement the Code of Conduct correctly. **X(Sti)** was also unaware that the Code of Conduct could be used effectively to discipline the learners to the extent that the learner might end up being expelled if the correct procedure was followed. What was required was a better understanding of how the Code of Conduct is developed and implemented, through the training of all stakeholders in discipline policy development and implementation. Ama et al. (2020) attest that maintenance of discipline in schools and at home instils valuable skills and cultural morals in the learners. Disciplined schools attract more learners because everyone believes that a disciplined school produces quality learners.

Parents must provide a foundation of good discipline on which the school has the duty to build on. Consequently, the parents should always avail themselves when needed at school. However, the school must engage parents from the beginning of each year, provide them with a Code of Conduct and explain it to them. Learner discipline should not be an individual aspect. Ofori et al. (2018) emphasized that discipline in the society should begin at home. Indiscipline starts with the home because they are the children's first teachers. Therefore, the home and the school must interact and co-operate in instilling discipline.

The discipline policy appeared to be one-sided to those who did not undergo any training and understood it. It needed teachers to go through it and warranted the training of teachers to be able to understand and implement it. Segalo and Rambuda (2018) revealed that in South Africa, the common law principle of *in loco parentis* entitles teachers as the guardians in the school to discipline learners. However, in view of new legislation advancing children's rights, it is unclear as to the extent to which teachers can or do to enact the *in loco parentis* role.

If teachers are inadequately informed about school policies, learners will misbehave. Learners will defy any ready-made rules that they find in the classroom. They are aware that the class rules are supposed to be democratically developed. Meaning learners must be involved in participating in the development of their class rules. If they were involved, they would regard the rules as their own and comply with them. That is the requirement of developing the Code of Conduct, and it should be cascaded to class rules. The SGBs need to consult and involve the teaching and non-teaching staff, the parents, and learners to drafting school policies. Ama et al. (2020) indicate that discipline is most needed in schools because disrespect for teacher and school authority is rampant amongst the learners and as a result quality education becomes jeopardized. Good performance of schools and learners is very much linked to the participation of all stakeholders (parents, teachers, learners, and the private sector) in education.

According to Asare, Owusu-Mensah, Prince and Gyamera (2015) discipline is necessary for effective management, if the goals of the school are to be accomplished. There must be reasonable disciplinary policies and procedures in an effort to prevent and resolve students' discipline problems and ensure efficient functioning of schools and as such classrooms. Simeon and Favour (2020) attest that adequate rules and regulations, self-

discipline and punishment will in no doubt impact academic performance of students and the realization of educational goals.

It has been understood that among teachers' views on the perception of discipline at schools, the categories of order, rules, volunteering and autonomy have been of the utmost priority (Ugurlu, Beycioglu, Kondakci, Sincar, Yildirim, Ozer & Oncel, 2015). Cheruvalath and Tripathi argue that the solution is proper training for teachers and student-teachers in the use of counselling to manage behavioral problems. Also, full time counsellors can be appointed in schools. Furthermore, Ayeni and Amanekwe (2018) conducted a study on teachers' instructional workload management and students' academic performance in public and private schools and found that workload impacted negatively. Kutsyuruba, Klinger and Hussain (2015) indicated that school climate, safety and well-being of students are important antecedents of academic achievement. The authors provided a recommendation for future research on discussion of the implications for school policies and practices in the areas of school climate, safety and student success.

5. Limitations

The study was conducted in five schools of one district. Though the district has both public and private schools, the participants were only from the public Secondary Schools. The focus was only on education discipline policy on learner discipline and academic performance in public Secondary Schools in the district. The findings could not be generalized to other schools.

6. Recommendations

- The study made it evidently that the scholars still need to research education policies enormously because only learner education discipline policy findings are presented.
- Provision of training the stakeholders in public schools in policy development and implementation because it is an area that poses significant challenges in schools.
- Monitoring and evaluation of education policies to reveal the challenges in policy implementation and indicate if there is a need for support.
- Schoolteachers need to adopt a Code of Conduct in which learners and other stakeholders are allowed to participate in the preparation thereof.
- Learner discipline in the schools is the domain of the deputy principals, among other duties. So, they should liaise with the schoolteachers and ensure a pleasant climate for learning.
- Schoolteachers to study the new education policies and be empowered on how to implement them effectively and be able to assist other parties because discipline is a team venture.

7. Conclusion

The article aimed to explore and describe the schoolteachers' perceptions of education discipline policy on learners' academic performance in selected South African public Secondary Schools in the district. The participants believed that the introduction of the new education policies was the major cause of learner misconduct in their schools because they protected learners more than teachers, and learners could no longer be punished which rendered teachers ripped from the means to discipline learners. The findings revealed that participants were conscious about national education policies affecting learner discipline and academic performance negatively, because township schools fail to develop and implement the policies correctly and effectively.

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References

- Ama H. A., Moorad, F. R., & Mukhopadyay, S. (2020). Stakeholders' perceptions of their roles in enhancing discipline in rural community schools. *Journal of Education Research and Rural Community Development*, (2(2), 1-18. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4023101>. (Accessed 10/05/2025).
- Asare, A. S., Owusu-Mensah, F., Prince, L., & Gyamera, A. (2015). Managing school discipline: the students' and teachers' perception on disciplinary strategies. *British Journal of Psychology Research*, 3(2), 1-11, June 2015. www.eajournals.org. (Accessed 3/11/2025).
- Ayeni, A. J., & Amanekwe, A. P. (2018). Teachers' instructional workload management and students' academic performance in public and private secondary schools in Akoko North-East Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria.

- American International Journal of Education and Linguistics Research. 1(1), 2018. www.aceusa.org/journal/index.php/aijerlr. (Accessed 2/11/2025).
- Benton, F. (2017). Five misunderstandings about case study. *Qualitative Inquiry*, (12):2: 219-245.
- Biggam, J. (2018). *Succeeding with your masters' dissertation: A step-by-step handbook*. North America: Open University Press.
- Brozak, J. (2017). The importance of a low student-teacher ratio. <http://classroom.synonym.com>. (Accessed 7 April 2017).
- Cheruvath, R., & Tripathi, M. (2015). Secondary school teachers' perception of corporal punishment. A case study in India, *The Clearing House. A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas*, 88:4, 127-132. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00098655.2015.1045821>.
- De Buck, E., Vandekerckhove, P., & Hannes, K. (2018). Evidence-based guidance to assist volunteers working with at-risk children in a school context. *International Journal of Evidence-Based Healthcare*, 16:32-46.
- Department of Education South Africa Circular 129. (1998). *Teacher workload*. Pretoria: Tshwane South.
- Department of Basic Education South Africa. (2012). *Previously disadvantaged/independent schools: D4: Grade 12: NSC results*. Boston: Mc Graw Hill.
- Ebrahim, S. (2018). *Discipline in schools: What the law says you can and cannot do*. South Africa: Mail and Guardian.
- Education Regulations. (1957). *Education*. Republic of Mauritius: The Government Printer.
- Edinyang, S. D. 2017. Maintaining discipline in a school studies classroom. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology Research*, 3(2), 54-60.
- Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1994). Competing paradigms in qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds), *Handbook of qualitative research* (pp.105-117). Sage.
- Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage, Beverly Hills.
- Hammond, M., & Wellington, J. (2021). *Research methods the key concepts*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429058165>.
- Higton, J. (2017). *Teacher workload survey: Research report*. Institute for employment research. Warwick. University of Warwick.
- Honing, M. I. (2006). *New directions in education policy designs and successful policies*. New York: Sunny press. <https://www.nps.gov/features/malu/feat0002/wof/Thurgood.Marshall.htm-2015>. (Accessed 16 January 2019).
- India Centre for Media Studies-Institutional Review Bord (CMS-IRB). (2020). *Guidelines for ethical consideration in social research and evaluation in India*. New Delhi: Alok Srivastava.
- Jinot, B. L. (2017). A critical review of the current education system of Mauritius and the learner discipline problem in Mauritian state secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 8(1), (October). ISSN 2289-1552.
- Kabir, S. M. (2016). *Basic guidelines for research. An introductory approach for all disciplines*. Brook Zone Publication. Bangladesh.
- Korstjens, I., & Moser, A. (2017) Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 2: Context, research questions and designs. *European Journal of General Practice*, 23:(1), 274-279. DOI:10.1080/13814788.2017.1375090.
- Korstjens, I., & Moser, A. (2018). Series: Practical guidelines to qualitative research. Part 4: Trustworthiness and publishing. *European Journal of General Practice*, 24:(1), 120-124. DOI: 10.1080/13814788.2017.1375092.
- Kutsyuruba, B., Klinger, D. A., & Hussain, A. (2015). Relationships among school climate, school safety and student achievement and well-being: a review of literature. *Review of Education*, 3(2), 103-135. DOI:10.1002/rev3.3024.
- Leedy, P. D. (2019). *Practical research: Planning and design*. 8th edition. New York: Macmillan.
- Majid, U. (2018). *Research fundamentals: Study design, population, and sample size*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26685/urn.16>.
- Lumato, E., & Mwila, P. M. (2022). Stakeholders' perceptions about the use of alternative punishment in maintaining school discipline: A case of Bagamoyo District, Tanzania. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 36(3), 6-21. Article no. AJESS.92784 ISSN: 2581-6268.
- Meier, R. (2017). Addressing problems in integrated schools: Student-teacher perceptions regarding viable solutions for learner problems. *South African Journal of Education*, 25(3), 170-177.
- Mweshi, G. K., & Sakyi, K. (2020). Application of sampling methods for the research design. *Archives of Business Research*, 8(11), 180-193. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14738/ABR.811.9042>.
- Muwambo, P. (2016). *Quality as human development: A case study of teaching and learning in Zimbabwean universities*. PhD Thesis. Bloemfontein. University of Free State.

- Nash, P., Schlosser, A., & Scarr, T. (2016). Teachers' perceptions of disruptive behavior in schools: A psychological perspective. *Emotional and Behavioural Difficulties*, 21(2), 167-180. DOI:10.1080/13632752.2015.1054670.
- Ofori, K. N., Tordzro, G., Asamoah, E., & Achiaa, E. (2018). The effects of indiscipline on academic performance of junior high school students in the Fanteakwa District of Ghana. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(21).
- Otu, O. O., Obun, A. F., & Joseph, O. V. (2019). Students' perception towards management of discipline and their academic performance in Cross River State. *Global Journal of Academic Research (GJAR)*, Jan-March, 3(1). www.ijiem.com.ng. (Accessed 3/11/2025).
- PEC. (2018). Public Education Center. <http://www.pec.dc.org>. (Accessed 5/01/2022).
- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2022). *Essentials of nursing research: Appraising evidence for nursing practice*. 10th edition. Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer.
- Renuka, V., & Jonathan, J. (2015). *Designing your first research proposal: A manual for researchers in education and the social sciences*. Claremont. Juta.
- Rens. (2016). www.hsrcpress.ac.za/downloadpdf.php. (Accessed 10/05/2023).
- Republic of South Africa Government Gazette. (1997). Vol 387 No. 18256. Abolition of Corporal Punishment Act 33 of 1997. Cape Town. 5 September 1997.
- Segalo, L., & Rambuda, A. M. (2018). South African public-school teachers' views on right to discipline learners. *South African Journal of Education*, 38(2).
- Sepasgozar, S., Davis, S. R., & Loosemore, M. (2018). Dissemination practices of construction site's technology vendors in technology exhibitions. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 34(6). DOI:10.1061/(ASCE)ME.1943-5479.0000650.
- Shalaway, L. (2015). Sure-fire Strategies for handling difficult students. Scholastic-teaching resources. <http://www.Scholastic.com/teachers/> Article 25 sure-fire strategies-handling-difficult students.
- Sharma, B. (2018). *Processing of data analysis*. Biostatistics and Epidemiology International Journal. Opology Press. India.
- Sileyew, K. J. (2019). Chapter research design and methodology. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.85731>.
- Simba, N. O. (2016). Impact of discipline on academic performance of learners in public primary schools. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(6).
- Simeon, W. E., & Favour, N. L. (2020). Impact of discipline on students' academic performance in public junior secondary school in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Psychology & Social Development* 8(4), 95-104. www.seahipaaj.org. (Accessed 1/11/2025).
- Sreekumar, D. (2023). What is Research Methodology? Definition, Types, and examples. academic writing guides. August 28, 2023. <https://paperpal.com/blog/academic-writing-guides/what-is-research-methodology/>
- Stelmack, B. (n.d). Parental involvement: A research brief for practitioners of University Alberta. https://www.academia.edu/8232520/Literature_Synopsis?Email_work_card=view-paper.
- Subbiah, C. (2015). *The role of learners in the management of discipline in urban public schools in KwaZulu-Natal*. Med Dissertation. Pretoria. Unisa.
- Ugboko, F. E., & Adediwura, A. A. (2012). A study of principal supervisory strategies and secondary school discipline. *Journal of Education and Social Research*, 2(1), 41-49. www.sokanu.com/teacherassistant. (Accessed 12/04/2020).
- Ugurlu, C. T., Beycioglu, K., Kondakci, Y., Sincar, M., Yildirim, M. C., Ozer, N., & Oncel, A. (2015). The views of teachers towards perception of discipline in schools. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 197, 120-125. www.sciencedirect.com. (Accessed 10/10/2025).